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Appraisal Analysis Of Farmfex Hybrid Agro Resources Nigeria's Advertisements

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ABSTRACT

Advertising plays a crucial role in agribusiness by shaping consumer perceptions, influencing purchasing decisions, and enhancing brand credibility. This study examines the use of Appraisal Theory, a framework within Systemic Functional Linguistics (SFL), in Nigerian agribusiness advertisements. Using promotional texts from FarmFex Hybrid Agro Resources Nigeria, the study investigates how Attitude, Engagement, and Graduation are strategically employed to persuade potential customers, establish credibility, and position the company as an industry leader. The findings reveal that Affect is used to evoke trust and emotional appeal, Judgment constructs an image of reliability and expertise, and Appreciation highlights product superiority. Engagement is used to balance authoritative claims and external validation, while Graduation intensifies persuasiveness through quantification and emphasis. This study contributes to research on business discourse, advertising strategies, and agricultural marketing by demonstrating how evaluative language influences consumer engagement in agribusiness advertisements.

Keywords: Appraisal analysis, FarmFex Agro Resources, SFL, advertisements, persuasion

1. INTRODUCTION

Food security and agricultural transformation are the key policy goal in the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development. One thing is to provide food security and agricultural transformation and another thing is to use language effectively to persuade people to support this transformation. Agro industries have a role to play in providing necessary information in the area of selling farm implements, fertilizers, pesticides, herbicides, among others since “agriculture and related industries significantly influence the global food supply chain” (Gómez & Lee, 2023). According to Hassen and Bilali, (2022), food security is “affected by soaring food prices which is driven by the economic fallout of COVID-19 pandemic and the disruption of global commodity markets due to the Russia-Ukraine conflict.” In order to combat the challenges of food security and agricultural transformation, there has been development of new technologies to support e-agriculture (Kante & Ndayizigamiye, 2020; Kuhn et al., 2022; Benyam, et al. 2021; Bolfe et al., 2020). Language plays a vital role in dissemination of information related to agribusiness. Agribusiness is a vital sector of Nigeria’s economy, contributing significantly to food security, employment, and economic development. As global concerns about sustainability and food accessibility grow, agribusiness companies increasingly rely on advertising to promote their products, innovations, and commitment to

sustainable farming practices. Agribusiness advertisements focus on sustainability and food security, scientific and technological advancements in agriculture, and farmer empowerment and economic development.

Effective advertising strategies play a key role in influencing potential investors, farmers, and policymakers. The language plays an evaluative function which shows the opinion and stance of language users towards a person, a thing or any entity (Hunston, 2011). The FarmFex Agro Resources uses language as a means to express its attitude and convey its judgment or evaluation in terms of whether people or things are good or bad.

FarmFex as Agro Resources makes use of evaluative language in its advertisements of oil palm seedlings. It is used to establish and negotiate the relationship with the addressee, inviting him or her to share the same attitude. The method of advertisement by FarmFex is anchored on evaluative language which expresses its attitude as a crucial tool of persuasion. Evaluative language serves as a weapon which the agribusiness advertisers use to persuade their customers to buy their products.

Despite the growing importance of agribusiness in Nigeria, little attention has been paid to the persuasive linguistic strategies employed in its advertisements. Specifically, the use of evaluative language, which plays a critical role in persuasion, has not been adequately analysed through Systemic Functional Linguistics (SFL). Understanding how Appraisal resources function in agribusiness advertisements will provide valuable insights into advertising discourse and agricultural marketing strategies. This study therefore addresses the following research objectives to:

1. analyse the use of Attitude (Affect, Judgment, Appreciation) in FarmFex advertisements;
2. examine how Engagement strategies are used to position claims and build credibility;
3. investigate how Graduation enhances the persuasive impact of advertisements and;
4. demonstrate how linguistic choices contribute to consumer engagement and brand perception.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Systemic Functional Linguistics (SFL) and Appraisal Theory

Systemic Functional Linguistics (SFL) is concerned with how language functions in social contexts, focusing on how meaning is structured to achieve communicative goals (Halliday & Matthiessen, 2014). Within SFL, Appraisal Theory (Martin & White, 2005) provides a framework for analysing evaluative language in texts. It consists of three main subsystems:

1. **Attitude:** It focuses on the realisation of emotions (Affect), social evaluation (Judgment), and aesthetic assessment (Appreciation).
2. **Engagement:** It deals with how authors of texts position claims and acknowledge other perspectives.
3. **Graduation:** It focuses on the exploration of how language is intensified or downplayed to increase persuasiveness.

Several scholars have employed Martin & White's (2005) approach in their investigations of business discourse (Magocha, 2010; Pounds, 2011). As a result, this framework appears to be a workable analytical framework for this investigation. But before her Appraisal Framework can be used in the context of commercial discourse, Pounds (2011) also points out that it must be modified. In her research, Pounds alters the categories and concentrates on the analysis of appreciation, a subcategory of attitude. The four criteria are: 1) Intensification; 2) Pleasantness; 3) Quality; and 4) Emotional Impact. With new categories like quality and pleasantness that are contextualised to property advertising discourse, the framework is better suited for the analysis of online discourse about real estate due to the modifications.

2.2 Persuasive Strategies in Agribusiness Advertising in Nigeria

Advertising relies on persuasive language to influence consumer behaviour, build brand identity, and establish credibility (Cook, 2001). There are previous studies on advertising that made use of persuasion through euphemism to reach out to their target audience (Limfrot-Ham, 2005; Gómez, 2009, Bolinger, 1987; Myer, 1994; Onipede, 2023). Studies have shown that evaluative language enhances consumer trust and product appeals (Goddard, 2018). Aristotle's ethos, pathos, and logos framework (as cited in

McQuarrie & Mick, 1996) remains relevant in modern advertising, where brands establish credibility (ethos), evoke emotions (pathos), and provide logical reasoning (logos).

Some key persuasive strategies in advertising include:

Emotional appeal (pathos): Using emotional language to create a personal connection with consumers.

Expert authority (ethos): Citing research, certifications, or professionals to enhance credibility.

Logical reasoning (logos): Providing factual claims, statistics, and benefits to persuade buyers.

Agribusiness advertisements in Nigeria focus on food security, technological advancements, and economic benefits.

3. METHODOLOGY

This study adopts a qualitative discourse analysis approach to examine evaluative language in agribusiness advertisements. The data for this study were extracted from FarmFex Hybrid Agro Resources Nigeria's official website, social media platforms such as Facebook and WhatsApp. The data containing relevant advertisements were purposively selected for our analyses. The advertisements were analysed using Appraisal Theory, focusing on: 1) Attitude (Affect, Judgment, and Appreciation); 2) Engagement (Monoglossic vs. Heteroglossic stance) and; 3) Graduation (Force and Focus).

4. DATA ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION

4.1 Attitude Analysis

Affect (Emotional Appeal)

Emotional engagement is a key persuasive technique in agribusiness advertisements. The use of affective language fosters trust and connection between sellers and potential customers.

This emotional appeal reduces uncertainty, making potential buyers feel secure in choosing this company.

"We're confident that we can bring you the results you need." (Positive Affect – Assurance)

"We are committed to supporting sustainable agriculture and improving the livelihoods of farmers."

(Positive Affect – Commitment)

Judgment (Credibility & Expertise)

"We work closely with agricultural experts..." (Judgment – Professionalism)

"Our hybrid oil palm seedlings are sourced from the best genetic lines..." (Judgment – Product

Superiority)

Judgment evaluates competence, reliability, and ethical commitment. Agribusiness firms use judgmental language to build trust by aligning their products with expert knowledge.

By positioning their products as genetically superior, the advertisement constructs a scientific credibility narrative, convincing buyers of its reliability.

Appreciation (Product Quality & Value)

"High-yield super hybrid oil palm variety..." (Appreciation – Productivity)

"Our seedlings undergo rigorous quality checks..." (Appreciation – Reliability)

Appreciation relates to how products are valued in terms of efficiency and usefulness. In agribusiness marketing, this often involves product durability, performance, and sustainability.

This statement effectively merges quantitative validation with qualitative appreciation, reinforcing the seedlings' reliability and profitability.

4.2 Engagement Analysis

Monoglossic Claims: "Our major farms are strategically located in Ibadan and Edo state." (Authoritative tone, no alternative views)

Heteroglossic Positioning: "Join over 8,000 successful farmers..." (Inviting discourse, engaging audience) "Join over 8,000 successful farmers who have turned their farms into profitable ventures!"

"Join over 8,000 successful farmers" implies inclusivity and shared success.

"Turned their farms into profitable ventures" suggests guaranteed prosperity.

Some claims in advertisements are monoglossic, meaning they do not entertain counterarguments.

By presenting strong, unqualified claims, the advertisement positions the company as an authoritative expert. Engagement concerns how advertisements acknowledge or exclude alternative perspectives. Agribusiness ads blend monoglossic and heteroglossic strategies to control consumer perception. Some engagement strategies invite the audience to participate in the advertised narrative.

This interpersonal engagement technique encourages participation by presenting existing users as role models.

4.3 Graduation Analysis

Force (Intensification): “We have successfully trained over 1,000 young farmers...” (Numbers to strengthen credibility)

Focus (Sharpening): “Ensuring food security, sustainability, and profitability...” (Narrowing focus to key aspects)

"Empowering a sustainable and prosperous agricultural future."

"To date, we have successfully trained over 1,000 young farmers who are thriving in the Nigerian agricultural sector and across Africa."

"Empowering" conveys agency and action, making the company sound proactive.

"Sustainable and prosperous" amplifies long-term benefits, aligning with global sustainability goals.

"Over 1,000 young farmers" quantifies impact, making the company's contributions tangible.

"Thriving across Africa" extends geographical reach, suggesting regional authority.

Graduation enhances persuasiveness by increasing the strength of claims or emphasizing numerical superiority. This strategic amplification increases emotional appeal while linking the brand to economic and environmental responsibility.

Using large numerical references is a persuasive strategy that increases credibility and market influence.

5. CONCLUSION

This study has examined the appraisal stance in the selected FarmFex advertisements. It was revealed that 1) attitude constructs trust and product credibility; 2) engagement balances authoritative claims with external validation; and 4) graduation amplifies persuasiveness through intensification and quantification. The implications for agribusiness marketing is that it should optimize evaluative language to enhance consumer trust. The linguistic research contributes to business discourse analysis within SFL.

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Appendixes

We're Confident That We Can Bring You The Results You Need

Our major farms are strategically located in Ibadan and Edo state, where we provide adequate care to our verified seedlings, ensuring their readiness for customers during the planting season.

While our nursery farms are primarily situated in Nigeria, we are actively planning to expand our reach in establishing mega nursery farms in other African countries, fostering regional agricultural development through our high-quality hybrid seedlings and professional services.

Our hybrid oil palm seedlings are sourced from the best genetic lines, ensuring superior growth rates and high oil yield.

We work closely with agricultural experts to deliver seedlings that meet the demands of modern farming practices.

Our verified hybrid coconut seedlings are known for their robustness and high productivity because they are nurtured under optimal conditions, ensuring they are healthy and ready for planting.

We are committed to supporting sustainable agriculture and improving the livelihoods of farmers.

We're All about Sustainability

Empowering a sustainable and prosperous agricultural future, FarmFex Hybrid Agro Resources Nigeria strives to be Africa's leading provider of high-quality hybrid oil palm and coconut seedlings, expert agricultural services, and comprehensive education.

We Believe That Food Should Be Easily Accessible

We envision a continent where food security, profitability, and environmental stewardship thrive, fostering a community of successful farmers and agri-entrepreneurs. We help farmers maximize their yield and profitability while promoting availability and security. Our seedlings undergo rigorous quality checks and are verified for disease resistance, drought resistance and high performance leading to farmers' profitability.

We're Interested in Grooming the Younger Generation

Each year, we organize free agricultural training programs for young individuals, enlightening them about the countless benefits, opportunities, and immense wealth that can be attained through agriculture. To

date, we have successfully trained over 1,000 young farmers who are thriving in the Nigerian agricultural sector and across Africa.

Join over 8,000 Successful Farmers Who Have Turned Their Farms into Profitable Ventures Using Our Well Nurtured High-yield Super Hybrid Oil Palm Seedlings!

Our high-yield super hybrid oil palm variety has helped over 8,000 farmers grow their oil palm farms into profitable businesses. These well-nurtured seedlings are nursed for productivity and maximum yield within two years and six months of planting them. Whether you're just starting or looking to expand your farm, our seedlings can make you your first biggest profit margin ever. You can start today with the same trusted seedlings that are already helping so many farmers create wealth!

FarmFex Hybrid Agro Resources Nigeria is a leading agricultural company in Nigeria. Our core mission is ensuring food security, sustainability and profitability in agriculture, by empowering individuals to become successful farmers.

Farm Setup and Planting Services

We will help you to establish your next big farm the way we have helped other investors to establish theirs. We do this by ensuring proper layout and optimal planting techniques, positioning each seedling at the exact spot where they would access enough airflow, sunlight and required nutrient that would help them experience rapid growth and massive yield.

Farm Maintenance Services

We offer ongoing farm maintenance services/guidelines to our farmers. Planting seedlings without proper maintenance services is as good as not venturing into agriculture, that is why we offer ongoing farm maintenance services/guidelines, including pest management, fertilization, and weed control, this is to help farmers achieve the best possible results throughout the growing season.

Agriculture Training & Consulting

Our expertise extends beyond product sales as we provide coaching and training services to young farmers.

Our major farms are strategically located in Ibadan and Edo state, where we provide adequate care to our verified seedlings, ensuring their readiness for customers during the planting season. While our nursery farms are primarily situated in Nigeria, we are actively planning to expand our reach in establishing mega nursery farms in other African countries should align with sustainability and food security narratives to attract policy support and funding.